

Study on Mechanical Properties of Woven Hemp With Titanium Resin Composition

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ABSTRACT

An attempt has been made to develop novel polymer based nano composite material reinforced with natural fibre, synthetic fillers at both micro and nano- levels with increased performance in terms of mechanical properties. This work involves development of a new nano-composite material consisting of L-12 epoxy resin, Titanium at nano, hemp fibres at micro levels. The percentage composition of hemp fibres is varied from 0.3%, 0.5% and 0.7% by weight of the holding matrix, A fixed dosage of Titanium Nano particle of 0.3wt% of holding matrix is taken. A suitable surface modification method is employed for natural fibre treatment in order to adhere the nano-particles, this paper shall be dealing with the surface adhesion by corona method. Surfactants like Noah and KMnO₄ were applied on the fibres. Fibers used as reinforcement with epoxy to form composite material to enhance the adhesion between the fillers and holding matrix alkalisation. To determine interferential adhesion and homogeneous distribution of fibres in the holding matrix Spectroscopic analysis such as Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) and scanning electron microscope (SEM) were conducted. Mechanical testing like tensile and three-point bending tests were carried out. Among the varied 0.5% of Noah and KMnO₄ treated hemp containing Titanium has given optimistic results as compared to other dosage levels.

Keywords-
Titanium;
hemp fiber;
Fourier
transform
infrared;
SEM;
KMnO₄;
alkalization;
epoxy; Noah

1. INTRODUCTION

Materials considered exclusively as assurance routinely comes as free fills supported with foil or paper. The conventional outlining materials are surely not skilled to get the need of such uncommon properties, for example, fantastic, bring down thickness and lower leading property. The energy on an exceptionally fundamental level continuing, financially shrewd and light-weight protection materials is thus developing very much requested. Composite materials are supplanting conventional materials, as a result of their unrivaled properties, for example, high quality to-weight proportion, high mechanical quality and least warm extension. Glass fiber and banana fiber are the two fillers utilized as a touch of present examination fortified just in epoxy gum to convey two methodologies of composites by carefully assembled structure. The proposed model is then bolstered through testing that drove in controlled research focus circumstances. As far as possible for attestation is to debilitate the sparkle stream and manage temperature. It fills in as a warmth opposing material and subsequently it keeps the distinctive contraptions and reliable articles which ought to be kept up at determined temperature go A warm security execution

of the composites which gets influenced by the three sections, i.e. strong conductivity, gas conductivity, and warmth radiations. Natural fiber strengthened polymer composites turned out to be more appealing because of their high particular quality, lightweight, biodegradability, and environment warmth. Normal fiber mixed with fabricated fiber-reinforced polymer composites are finding extended applications. The goals for the insignificant exertion, on to mind boggling degree fundamental level ambitious, true blue and light-weight certification materials is thusly opening up all around asked. Arranged and focal both the fibers have dumbfounding confirmation mechanical properties.

1.1 Composition

In setting of this, the ebb and flow investigate has been attempted to deliver a move at the aftereffects of including the isolative short fibers the mechanical property of polymer gum. The present work concentrates on the inconvenience composites of epoxy For this the banana strands and glass filaments are used for enhancing the farthest traverse. There are numerous components that can affect the execution of normal fiber fortified composites. Beside the hydrophilic

method for fiber, the properties of the customary fiber braced composites can similarly be influenced by fiber content/measure of filler. At the point when all is said in done, high fiber substance is required to achieve tip top of the composites. In this way, the effect of fiber substance on the properties of normal fiber braced composites is particularly importance. It is much of the time watched that the development in fiber stacking prompts to an addition in tractable properties. Another essential component that on a very basic level effects the properties and interfacial qualities of the composites is the get ready parameters used. Accordingly, suitable get ready techniques and parameters must be meticulously picked remembering the true objective to yield the perfect composite things. This article hopes to review the reported wears down the effects of fiber stacking, engineered medications, delivering strategies and process parameters on malleable properties of consistent fiber sustained composites. Trademark fiber polymer composites (NFPC) are a composite material including a polymer framework inserted with surprising reliable strands, similar to HEMP, oil palm, sisal, kenaf, and flax. For the most part, polymers can be sorted out into two portrayals, thermoplastics and thermo sets. The structure of thermoplastic framework materials includes potentially a couple dimensional sub-atomic, so these polymers tend to make gentler at a raised warmth range and move back their properties all through cooling. Then again, thermo sets polymer can be portrayed as fundamentally cross-related polymers which cured utilizing just warmth, or utilizing warmth and weight, furthermore light lighting up. Thusly, legitimate process methods and parameters should be altogether picked with a particular true objective to get the best qualities of making composite. The blend bit of normal fibers moreover bigly influences the characteristics of the composite addressed by the rate of cellulose, hemicelluloses, lignin, Ceramic Matrix Composites (CMC) Pottery is depicted by touchy quality, hardness, separating and oxidation resistance and unrivaled lifted temperature properties. The blowing structure composites have a potential to use as a higher temperature as comparison of others polymer and we can say that metal framework composite and it has also not containing the distant diverse characteristics which is its natural property so far from the beginning. Focal mud structures are oxides, carbides, nitrides, borides, glasses, glass-soil creation and silicates. The supporting of material for improving mechanical properties are as strands, stubbles or particulates. These composites are facilitated by sintering, hot beating, hot isotactic crushing, catch, and reaction holding and start blend. One of the focal concentrations in passing on let go framework composites is to collect the robustness. Conventionally, it is trusted and purpose of actuality habitually found, that there is a modification in the quality and robustness of let go framework composites.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

The natural fiber containing composites are more environmentally friendly, and are used in various applications, as results of increasing demand for environmentally friendly materials and desired to reduce the cost of traditional fibers. Nagamadhu M et al observed that 4% NaOH treatment gives hopefully good results as compare to the untreated and 6% treated samples [1]. Jiyas N et al worked on mechanical and interlaminar properties of woven banana-glass fiber reinforced epoxy composites [2]. Mohammad Asim et al worked on the effects of NaOH, silane and NaOH-silane treatments for natural fibers [3]. Easwara Prasad G L et al concluded that impact strength of both untreated and 5% NaOH treated sisal fiber embedded polyester matrix composites increases with increase in their thickness and fiber volume fraction [4]. Jai Inder Preet Singha et al worked on mechanical properties for treated and non-treated natural fiber reinforced [5]. Muhammad Khusairy Bin Bakria et al observed that treated fiber composites have superior properties as compared with untreated fiber composites [6]. Nag Tien Lama et al investigated the Utilizing cellulose from sugarcane bagasse mixed with poly (vinyl alcohol) for tissue engineering scaffold fabrication. [7] Milena Martelli Tosia et al observed changes in the chemical composition and structure of soybean straw treated with alkali 5% and 17.5% [8]. Mohammad Asim et al concluded that the scanning electron microscope indicates that silane treated fibers have less impurities, lignin and hemicelluloses removed than those by other chemical treatments [9]. M.J.M. Ridzuan et al observed that the effect of soaking time during the alkali treatment on the tensile strength of Napier grass fiber [10]. R. Yahaya et al concluded treated kenaf improves the mechanical properties of hybrid composites [11]. N. Venkateshwaran et al studied on alkali (NaOH) of various concentrations (0.5%, 1%, 2%, 5%, 10%, 15% and 20%) was used to treat the fiber surface and the effect of these concentrations on the mechanical and visco-elastic behavior of the composites were carried out [12]. E. O. Achukwu et al concluded that alkali treatment improve avudeen et al worked on the mechanical properties of banana, Kenaf and banana/Kenaf fiber-reinforced hybrid polyester composites [13]. Layth Mohammed et al concluded that alkaline treatment, silane treatment and acetyl treatment of OPF improved the adhesion between the fibers and epoxy polymer [14]. Allan C. Manalo et al observed that the improvement in the mechanical properties of the composites was achieved with the treatment of the bamboo fibers with sodium hydroxide. This improvement is due to the enhancement in the adhesion between the bamboo fibers and the polyester resin [15]. Mohammad Asima et al investigated with the aim to improve their compatibility with polymer matrices. [16]. Jun-Seok Yeo et al invested on the effect of chemical surface treatment on the fracture toughness of micro fibrillated cellulose [17]. Sekhar Das et al observed that the effect of woven HEMP fabric and layering pattern effect on mechanical properties of newspaper/woven HEMP fabric hybrid composites [18]. Raghuvveer H. Desai et al made

review paper is collective information about the research done until date on areca fiber chemical composition, characterization, and physical properties. T. Vinod Kumar et al worked on characterized and synthesized through the various mechanical tests and also the results were compared [19]. R. Yahayaa et al studied on the effect of layering sequence and chemical treatment on mechanical properties of woven Kenaf and Kevlar composite [20]. Michael George et al investigated on evaluation of the environmental impact of chemical methods.

2.1 Mould Preparation

The present work initially deals in preparing mold a cleaned, smooth of a mild Steel plate of size 250 X 200 X 4 mm were used as shown in the figure 1 and figure 2. The fabrication of the composite material was carried out through the hand-lay-up technique Fabrication of Composite Laminates. The composite laminates were prepared by the hand lay-up process. Composite was made using mild steel mold measuring 250 X 200 X 4 mm length, width and depth respectively. The bottom slab of the mold was thoroughly cleaned with thinner; smoothen by wax polish which acts as releasing agent and the same procedure followed by top slab also. To help complete removal of the composite from the mold, a polyethylene sheet is laid on the clean and dry mould before fabrication of the composites.

Figure 1 Mould Box

Figure 2 Fabrication of composites

Mechanical Testing The mechanical testing is carried out to understand the mechanical performance of the composites by using Universal Testing Machine (UTM).

2.2 Tensile Test

Tensile strength is a measure of a materials ability to resist being pulled apart. The tensile test is generally

performed by Universal Testing Machine (UTM) which is presented in figure 3. Tensile testing of specimens prepared according to ASTM D-638, the specimen is 160 X 12.5 X 4 mm length, width and depth respectively as and, the tensile modulus and elongations at the break of the composites were calculated from the load-displacement curve four specimens were tested for each set of samples and the mean.

2.3 Flexural Test

The flexural test is performed by three point bending method according to ASTM D-790 represented in figure 4.8. The specimen is 127 X 12.7 X 4 mm length, width and depth respectively, four specimens were tested, and the average was calculated, the specimen was freely supported by a beam, the maximum load was applied in the middle of the specimen until the it fracture and breaks. The test results include flexural strength and displacement.

Figure 3 Tensile specimen

Figure 4 point bent test

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter highlighted the effect of Titanium treatment with different percentages of concentrations, the experimental results of tensile, flexural and impact strength were discussed and reported in figures 3-5. From the experimental results the tensile strength of unmixed 5, 10 and 15% treated composites are 78.3, 115.5, 135.12 and 120.12MPa respectively and figures 3 and also observed that the variations in tensile strength with the increases in the Titanium treatment up to 10%, and further increases in the % of Titanium concentrations for 15% that leads to decreases in the tensile strength. Figure 4 shows that the experimental results of flexural strength of untreated and treated fabrics composite and also shows

that the flexural strength of treated composite are more than the untreated composite.

Figure 5 load displacement curve

4. CONCLUSION

From the above study, we can see the more effective utilization of natural fibers in polymer composites. NaOH treatment: the 5% NaOH treatment gave the increment of strength by 34 times and load carrying capacity by 9 times in tensile test with respect to pure epoxy sample. 3% Permanganate on further treatment has increased the load carrying capacity by 1.3 times and the deflection has decreased by 2.9 times with respect to pure epoxy sample. The composite is stable until the temperature of 344 degree and then burns with exothermic reaction. Treatment of natural fibers helps increase the strengths of the matrix. The results from tensile test of the material we found that 3% alkaline treated hemp yielded more than five times that of untreated hemp. Whereas with the increase in reinforcement the strength is reduced. In case of permanganate treatment the higher strength was found at 5% potassium permanganate treatment. The reason for decreased strength of the untreated hemp may be improper dispersion of hemp and the bonding capability of hemp with the epoxy. With the specialized chemical treatment fibers become rougher and bonding becomes easier. Cellulose depolymerize exposing short length crystallites. Thus we can conclude that treatment of hemp fibers help achieving higher strengths.

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